

Predicting Green Purchase Behavior: An Empirical Study Using Theory of Reasoned Action

Goutam Saha & Benazir Ishaque

Abstract

This paper aims to predict the effect of attitude, motivation to comply, and normative belief (others' expectations and behavior) on green purchase intention and behavior. The theory of reasoned action (TRA) model was adopted to investigate the green purchase behavior of Bangladeshi consumers. The judgmental sampling technique was used to collect data from 229 Bangladeshi consumers and IBM AMOS 24 was used for structural equation modeling, model fitness test, and hypothesis testing. This paper found that motivation to comply, normative belief of others' expectations, and normative beliefs of others' behavior influence green purchase intention, which consequently affects green purchase behavior. Contrary to our expectation, this study did not find significant relationship between attitude and purchase intention. The authors believe that this paper will act as a reference point in explaining consumers' green purchase behavior.

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About Author (s)

Goutam Saha (Corresponding Author), Department of Business Administration (DBA), Bangladesh Army University of Science and Technology, Saidpur Cantonment, Nilphamari, Bangladesh.

Benazir Ishaque, Department of Business Administration (DBA), Notre Dame University Bangladesh.

Introduction

Presently both organizations and consumers are being more concerned and cautious about the environment. Environmental consumption or green consumption has resulted from protecting the environment from perpetual decay (Moisander, 2007). With the proclamation of 1990 as the "Earth Decade" or "Environmental Decade," the environment has become a contentious societal issue (Baumann & Rex, 2006). This era showed rapid growth in green consumerism resulting from the shift towards greener products (Prothero, 1990; Vandermerwe and Oliff, 1990). The driving force behind this shift can be named as "green movement" (Pierre and Prothero, 1997), here 'green' sheds light on the basic problems regarding not only the environment but also social, economic, legal, and technological. Previously the focus was on the impact of society and business on the environment but in this movement, it shifted towards vice-versa, the impact of environment on the society and business. Such issues are the most talked about topic around the world. Green products are gaining popularity among consumers as an option to reduce the environmental impact on health issues (Nekmahmud & Fekete-Farkas, 2020). Consumers who feel the need for uniqueness and self-expressive benefits tend to buy green products (Afsar & Jia 2018). Nowadays these are influencing peoples' purchasing decisions to some extent, consciously or subconsciously. So now the question arises is what a green product is? Any product that is made of organic ingredients, non-toxic, recyclable, and eco-friendly can be a green product. Customers usually prefer buying green products from well-known organizations (Suki, 2013). Consumers are greatly motivated to exert green purchasing behavior if they have the willingness and ability to pay for the products (Adrita et al., 2020;). Bangladesh is a densely populated developing country. As Bangladesh is thriving in its industrial sector, the increasing number of factories are injecting an increasing amount of greenhouse gases into the environment. Not only that but also to accommodate these industries and to back them up with energy and power, the demolition of major natural resources is increasing as well. This speedy industrial growth has some advantages too. It has aided in creating employment opportunities, enhancing the standard of life, eradicating poverty, and developing the socio-economic structure of the country (Zohir, 2001). Bangladesh is on its way to achieving SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals) where sustainable development can be expressed as the development that fulfills the needs of the present generation by making sure that the future generations can meet their needs in the same way (Dresner, 2002). Bangladesh has already made recognizable progress in meeting the first three goals which are- hunger, poverty, and public health. The way to achieve these SDGs will have many hurdles, as the country has to make sure its people have access to clean water, sanitation, sustainable industrialization, innovation, etc. If the people of Bangladesh incorporate the concept of green purchasing or green consumption and environmentalism in their daily life, it would lead them to attain these sustainable development goals as well. However, in Bangladesh, very fewer studies are done on this environmentalism and green purchasing issue. Hence, understanding the Bangladeshi consumers' intent toward green purchasing is very pivotal for the government, manufacturers, and marketers. In this study, we are to investigate how consumers feel about green purchasing. The study focuses on answering three research questions- i. What factors are responsible for exerting green consumption behavior? ii. To what extent do attitude, motivation to comply, normative belief in others' expectations, normative belief in others' behavior, and purchase intention influence to exert green purchase behavior? iii. How can concerned authorities work on these factors to influence people to exert green purchase behavior? To answer these research questions empirically, the study has used a model called TRA. The theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) was proposed in 1975 by Fishbein and Ajzen to predict human behavior. The study overall tries to shed light on Bangladeshi consumers' green purchase behavior and how it can be enhanced so that Bangladesh can move on to a greener future.

Literature Review

The idea of environmentalism has been gaining support from customers for more environmentally responsible consumption (Han et al., 2009; Kalafatis et al., 1999). Consumers these days are more conscious about their consumption and the effect it has on the environment (Kilbourne et al., 2009; Laroche et al., 2001), and they are doing so for the benefit of their future generations. As a result, they are more interested than ever in purchasing products that are friendly to the environment. In 1975, Fishbein and Ajzen came up with the idea for what would become known as the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) to explain and forecast human behavior. Attitude and subjective norms are the two primary components that make up the TRA. Together, they are responsible for making accurate predictions regarding future conduct. Green transportation (Carruset al., 2008; S. Farag and G. Lyons, 2010); green recreation (D. J. Yang, M. R. Kao; C. Y. Loem and Y. S. Chen, 2011; T. Y. Chiu and W. H. Chih, 2012); green shopping (Yang et al., 2012, Sparks et al., 1995); and green production (Wang et al., 2011), among (Boldero, 1995). A study on green consumers' awareness, attitudes and behavior who are in their adolescence showed that their green consumer behavior was greater when they showed a more positive attitude towards green food consumption (Lin, 2011). The possibility of consumers performing the act is more or less influenced by subjective norms. How promptly an individual takes part in any particular behavior can be sensed by his intention which is an instant precursor of behavior (Ajzen, 1985). According to Ajzen and Fishbein (1980), attitude means how any individual assesses behavior, it can be either positive or negative. Prior studies show that attitude usually has a positive effect on any person's intention (Ajzen, 1991; Baker et al., 2007; Cheng et al., 2006; Taylor and Todd, 1995). Consumer attitude and perceived behavioral control are strong predictors of purchase intention, but subjective norm does not play a role in this relationship (Paul et al., 2016). Now, subjective norms denote the provocation of important people in an individual's life to live up to their expectations (Ajzen, 1991; Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975). The purpose of individuals to engage in a specific activity is at the heart of TRA's perspective. In the context of this investigation, "intention" refers to a participant's willingness or preparedness to engage in the activity that is being studied (Han and Kim, 2010; Ajzen, 1985). When one considers the connection that exists between the subjective norms of a person and the behavioral intentions that person harbors, it is possible to assert that subjective norms have a beneficial effect on behavioral intention (Han et al., 2010; Taylor and Todd, 1995). Sheppard et al. (1988) provided evidence that TRA possesses the capacity for prediction, since they demonstrated that the model accurately predicted the intents of persons when applied in a variety of contexts. It has been established in a great number of earlier research that individuals' intentions are significantly impacted by the attitudes and norms that they hold (Dolnicar et al., 2012; Jorgensen et al., 2013; Marandu et al., 2010).

Attitude (A)

People's attitudes can be defined as positive or negative cognitive judgments, emotional experiences, or behavioral dispositions that they have towards specific events or concepts (Blackwell et al., 2006). Previous studies noted attitude as an evaluative appraisal (Bagozzi, 1992). A study on teen consumers highlighted that environmental attitude act as a motivator in green purchasing (Lee, 2008). Attitude is the ability to identify if a certain behavior is good or bad and to decide if a person is ready to act that way or not (Leonard et al., 2004). Ramayah et al. (2010) said that attitude also includes how people think their actions will affect other people. Attitude is the most important thing that comes before behavior intention (Kotchen and Reiling, 2000). Attitude and plans for behavior are linked in a good way (Chen and Tung, 2014). Also, this good relationship has been found in many different cultures when it comes to

green products (Mostafa, 2007). Previous research has shown that attitude has a positive effect on intention (Han and Yoon, 2015; Teng et al., 2014; Chen and Tung, 2014; Chen and Peng, 2012; Han et al., 2011; Han and Kim, 2010; Han et al., 2010, 2009). In the organic food choice, there was a positive association between attitude and intention (Dean et al., 2012; Ha and Janda, 2012; Zhou et al., 2013). From the literature review, we can assume that a positive attitude toward green products will make people more likely to want to buy green products. So, the study suggests that:

H1: The attitude toward buying green products is positively related to the intention to purchase green products.

Subjective Norm (SN)

Subjective norm is a concept that refers to the support of an individual's important group of people who approve or support a particular behavior. It also comprises the social pressure an individual feels upon him. Previous studies showed subjective norm as a pivotal determinant of intention (Lee, 2005; Baker et al., 2007; Han et al., 2010; Dean et al., 2012; Ha and Janda, 2012; Tengetal., 2014; Chen and Tung, 2014; Khare, 2015; Moser, 2015). Subjective norms can be categorized as motivation to comply, normative beliefs about others' expectations, and normative beliefs about others' behavior. In the study of Ajzen (1991); Han et al. (2010)), Hee (2000) the influence of others like- close friends, relatives, colleagues, or business partners have on people to act in a particular way was portrayed. While showing any distinct behavior people usually are influenced by this group of kin and peers. Hence, the study proposes that:

H2a: Motivation to comply with green consumption is positively related to purchase intention.

Beliefs that are considered normative are those that are held by the majority of people. As cited in (Ajzen, 2006). The term "normative belief" refers to a view that a specific action is expected or desirable in a given situation. Subjective standards, attitudes, and conduct intentions are all affected by these normative beliefs (Nordlund and Garvill, 2003). People are more likely to spend money on environmentally friendly goods if they believe that their loved ones are encouraging them to do so. As a result, people are more inclined to engage in this group activity of purchasing environmentally friendly products (Kumar, 2012). Thus, the following hypothesis can be formulated to be investigated in this study:

H2b: Normative beliefs about others' expectations are positively related to the intention to purchase green products.

Actions of other people in a person's social or personal networks may impact that person's behavior. Collectivist societies have members who believe that social norms are a fundamental way of perceiving life, and these people place a greater emphasis on the emotional side of decision-making rather than the rational cost-benefit analysis in a relationship. Furthermore, they believe that life should be lived according to social norms (Sinha et al., 2001). The members of collectivist cultures are more empathetic toward the environment rather than those who are of individualistic cultures. Based on the discussion, it can be hypothesized that:

H2c: Normative beliefs about others' behavior are positively related to the intention to purchase green products.

Purchase Intention (PI)

Intention is seen as both an antecedent to and the greatest predictor of behavior (Ajzen, 2002). Green Purchase Intention refers to a consumer's intention or purchasing behavior toward an environmentally sustainable product or brand after understanding its green characteristic. With the emergence of a green consumer sector, remanufacturing companies are actively developing relevant marketing methods to enhance green consumers' purchase intention (Jiménez-Parra et al. 2014). According to certain green marketing research, a positive view toward green products increases the green purchase intention. (Laroche et al., 2001; Smith et

al., 1994). Consumers that have a favorable attitude toward green products are more likely to buy them (Mostafa, 2007). According to the study by Teng (2009) consumers that have a good attitude about a brand have higher buy intentions for that brand. Customers' green purchasing intentions are influenced by green trust and it has a substantial mediating effect on consumption values and green purchasing intention (Amin et al., 2020). Therefore, this study proposes the following hypothesis:

H3: Purchase intention of green products has a positive relationship with purchase behavior.

In light of the aforementioned literature review, the researchers have developed a theoretical framework which is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework
Adapted from: Theory of Reasoned Action (Ajzen, 1991)

Research Methods

Nature of the Research: To predict the factors that influence Bangladeshi consumers to exert green purchase behavior, this study took a descriptive approach along with a structured questionnaire with a view to collecting quantitative data. Information from respondents was collected twice to measure their green purchase intention (January 2021 to April 2021) and green purchase behavior (September 2021 to January 2022).

Research Question: Several research questions were asked by the authors which were guided by the specific objectives of the problem and theoretical framework. These were as follows:
What factors are responsible for exerting green consumption behavior?
To what extent does attitude, motivation to comply, normative belief about others' expectations, normative belief about others' behavior, and purchase intention influence to exert green purchase behavior?
How can concerned authorities work on these factors to influence people to exert green purchase behavior?

Sources of Data: This paper used both primary and secondary data. Primary data were collected online and offline from the respondent via a structured questionnaire. Secondary data sources were collected from various published documents like books, journals, newspapers and magazines, and websites.

Target population, Sample size, and sampling techniques: The target population of this study is Bangladeshi consumers who have the slightest knowledge of green consumption and are willing to act in a green way on their consumption behavior. In order to fulfill the research objectives total of 363 respondents were chosen using the non-probability called judgmental sampling technique. The researchers used some graduates who had green knowledge. Considering the ease of access, less costly, and required less time the authors use this technique to collect primary data from the respondents (Malhotra and Das, 2015). In the first phase of data collection, it was possible to collect data from 319 respondents to measure their green purchase intention, and then it was possible to collect data from 299 respondents in the second phase. After scrutinizing the data 229 were considered for data analysis. Mishal et al., 2017 state that a sample size of more than 200 is adequate for structural analysis.

Questionnaire: To collect the data the questionnaire includes three-part: introduction, demographic, and behavior measurements to assess the relationship and impact (Sarker et al., 2012). A total of 29 items under TRA elements and 5 items on demographic characteristics of the respondents are covered on the questionnaire through a review of literature on the area under discussion. During the survey period, the questions were translated into the local language (Bengali) to clarify the meaning of the questions to the respective respondents. For this survey, a 7-point Likert scales (1-strongly agree to 7-strongly disagree) was assigned to assess the respondents.

Data Analysis Techniques: For analyzing the data obtained from the survey the researchers use IBM SPSS 25 (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) to analyze the frequency, factor analysis, mean, and standard deviation. IBM AMOS version 24 was used for structural equation modeling and model fitness. To evaluate the previously constructed scores, researchers used confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) to examine and implement a measurement model, as well as path analysis to analyze the supposed correlations stated in this study's analytical model. As a result, the researchers have applied a sophisticated statistical approach known as SEM.

Results and Discussions

Demographic Profile

Table 1

		Frequency	Percent
Sex	Male	144	62.9
	Female	85	37.1
	Total	229	100.0
Age	20-30	153	66.8
	31-40	43	18.8
	41-50	25	10.9
	51-60	6	2.6
	60+	2	.9
	Total	229	100.0
	Education	Graduate	103
Post Graduate		100	43.7
Others		26	11.4
Total		229	100.0
Occupation	Student	35	15.3
	Service Holder	141	61.6
	Business	30	13.1
	Others	23	10.0
	Total	229	100.0
Income level	Low	76	33.2
	Mid	148	64.6
	High	5	2.2
	Total	229	100.0

In this study Table: 1 illustrated the demographic profile of the respondents namely sex, age, educational qualification, occupation and income level. Based on the sex of the respondent the table showed that the majority of the participants were male which exactly 144 respondents (62.9%). On the other hand, the female respondents, were 85 (37.1%). Age was the next demographic character followed by sex. The results of the analysis of the respondents' descriptions showed that the major portion of the participants were 153 respondents aged 20-30 years (66.8%), 43 people aged 31-40 (18.8%), 25 respondents aged 41-50 (10.9%), respondents aged 51-60 years are 6 people (4%) and the least number of respondents were from the age group of 60 above with barely 1%. The third demographic character was the educational qualification which comes as a next. It can be seen that the percentage of graduate and post-graduated respondents was almost same with 45% (103 respondents) and 43.7 (100 respondents) respectively. Another group occupied only 11.4 %. (26 respondents). Occupation indicates the working status of the respondents and it was classified into four groups: student, service holder, business and others. Almost 62 % (141 respondents) of the respondents were service holder which was the highest percentile. The rest three groups such as students, business, and others were almost same with 15.3% (35 respondents), 13.1 % (30 respondents) and 10% (respondents) respectively. Lastly, Income owned by the respondents was the last characteristic to discuss. The mid income level group was highest with just over 65% (148 respondents) compare to only 2.2% for the high-income level and low-income level was 33.2% (75 respondents).

Sample adequacy

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's Tests are shown in Table 2. The purpose of this analysis is to prove the adequacy of sample. The value of KMO is .861 which is more than required value of .70. Thus, it can be said that the sample adequacy is adequate. Furthermore, Table 2 also illustrates that the probability value of the approximate Chi-Square associate with Bartlett's test of Sphericity was less than .05 indicating that the population correlation matrix is not an identity matrix.

Table 2 : KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.861
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	2294.341
	df	300
	Sig.	.000

Factor Analysis

The interrelation between components and green consumption was discovered using confirmatory factor analysis with AMOS 24. Scale reliability, convergent validities, and discriminating validities are all required in factor analysis. As a result, these analyses were done in phases. The alpha value and composite reliability were investigated first. Second, we looked at relative factor loading and average variance extraction (AVE). Finally, discriminating validity is measured using a comparison of coefficient correlations and the square root of AVE. Table 3 shows the mean, standard deviation, correlation, and square root of average variance extracted (AVE). Attitude, motivation to comply, normative belief others expectation, normative belief others' behavior, purchase intention and purchase behavior all have a positive association. The constructs' dependability can be assessed using multiple procedures. The first criterion is done by examining the loading of items of each construct. Since the values are higher than the suggested level .60, the item loadings of all the constructs provided in table 4 are appropriate. One item from attitude, motivation to comply, and three items from purchase behavior were canceled due to the value of the item loading being less than 0.60. Cronbach's alpha is the second measure, and it is likewise a measure of reliability. Cronbach's alpha is the

second measure, and it is likewise a measure of reliability. Cronbach's alpha has a minimum cutoff value of 0.7. (Hair et al., 2011). Cronbach's alpha values range from 0.729 to 0.811 for the constructs examined in this research, namely attitude, motivation to comply, normative belief others expectation, normative belief others behavior, purchase intention and purchase behavior. Since the calculated values of all the constructs are greater than 0.7, the measurements are acceptable for reliability (Hair et al., 2011). The measure of composite reliability determines the degree to which the construct's components indicate the latent construct. The composite reliability of the constructs in this study ranges from 0.778 to 0.878, which is higher than 0.7 (Gefen et al. 2000).

Table 3 : Correlations, Mean, Standard Deviation and Square Root of AVE

Construct	Attitude	Motivation to comply	Normative Belief Others' Expectations	Normative Belief Others Behavior	Purchase Intention	Purchase Behavior
Attitude	.708					
Motivation to comply	.469**	.711				
Normative Belief Others Expectations	.419**	.366**	.735			
Normative Belief Others Behavior	.338**	.378**	.546**	.749		
Purchase Intention	.420**	.420**	.449**	.422**	.710	
Purchase Behavior	.203**	.327**	.374**	.373**	.466**	.738
Mean	6.078	5.780	5.383	5.326	5.792	5.94
Standard Deviation	1.062	1.210	1.256	1.399	1.117	1.383

** p<0.01.

The diagonal elements shown in bold represent square root of AVE and other elements are the correlation.

Table 4: Factors, factor, loading, Average Variance extraction (AVE), Cronbach's Alpha (CA) value, Composite Reliability (CR)

Factors	Variable name	Factor Loading	AVE	Cronbach's Alpha (CA)	Composite Reliability (CR)			
Attitude	A1	.663	.501	.799	.878			
	A2	.798						
	A3	.639						
	A4	.690						
	A5	.676						
	A6	.788						
	A7	.721						
Motivation to comply	MTC2	.780	.581	.802	.806			
	MTC3	.760						
	MTC4	.747						
	NBOE1	.671						
Normative Belief Others Expectations	NBOE2	.744	.540	.729	.778			
	NBOE3	.784						
	NBOB1	.731						
	NBOB2	.769						
Normative Belief Others Behavior	NBOB3	.745	.560	.769	.793			
	PI1	.751						
	PI2	.670						
Purchase Intention	PI3	.775	.504	.811	.801			
	PI4	.634						
	PB4	.666				.544	.794	.781
	PB5	.795						
PB6	.746							

Convergent and discriminant validity was performed to check the validity of the constructs in this study. The amount of variance in the items that are explained by the constructs is indicated by the average variance extracted (AVE). Table 4 shows that all of the AVE values are greater than .5, indicating a satisfactory level of convergent validity. The square root of AVE must be greater than the correlation between the construct and the other construct in the model to determine discriminant validity (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). In all circumstances, the square root of AVE is greater than the correlation between the constructs, as seen in tables 3 and 4. As a result, all of the scales' discriminant validity was confirmed. As a result, all of the scales demonstrated reliability, convergent validity, and discriminant validity.

Table 5: Model fitness of measurement model

Goodness of fit	
χ^2 with 260 degree of freedom	444.887 (p<0.001)
χ^2/df	1.711
Goodness of fit index (GFI)	.873
Incremental fit index (IFI)	.913
Comparative fit index (CFI)	.912
Tucker-Lewis index (TLI)	.898
Normed fit index (NFI)	.814
Root mean square error of approximation (RESEA)	.056

The fit of the six-factor measurement model of consumer green purchase behavior constructs based on the correlation matrix of 23 measures ($\chi^2(260)= 444.887$ (p<0.001); GFI=.873; IFI=.913; CFI=.912; TLI=.898; NFI=.814; RESEA=.056) is acceptable. Except for the value of chi-square these results are acceptable which is significant. Joreskog and Sorbom(1993) and Bentler(1980) advised against the sole use of chi-square value in judging the overall fit of the model. In assessing the model fit of a single model the chi-square has a limited utility (Thompson, 2004). Despite the intrinsic limitation of Chi-square statistics, the other fit indexes have been considered as an alternative. The table denote that the chi-square to DOF ratio of the measurement model is below 3 (1.711) that indicated the 'fitness' of the model. The CFI and IFI value also reached at the recommended level of 0.90. The RMSEA of the model is below the cut-off value of 0.08 (Hair et al., 2011). Considering the values of various fit indices and relating them to the acceptable parameters mentioned in the literature, it may be determined that the study methodology and the data are well-matched.

Hypothesis Testing

After getting satisfactory results in the measurement model the authors evaluated the structural model. Initial model fit indices were evaluated. As shown in table 6, all the model fit indices (χ^2 (260)= 433.349 (p<0.001); GFI=.886; IFI=.941; CFI=.909; TLI=.875; NFI=.868; RESEA=.059) are acceptable. As displayed in table 6, H1 has 0.073 standardized regression weight (SRW) and 0.094 scalar estimates (SE), which is more than RSW. But, SE is supposed to be smaller than SRW. And significance value ($\beta= .457$, p<0.05) makes this hypothesis not significant. In terms of H2a, the SE (0.068) is way below the SRW (0.280) and, the significance value ($\beta=.005$, p<0.01) is significant too. So, these indicate that there is a positive relationship between motivation to comply and purchase intention. H2b shows that the value of SE (0.063) is less than SRW (0.275) and the significance value ($\beta=0.028$, p<0.05) is also significant. Thus, there is a significant relationship between normative belief others expectations and purchase intention. With regard to H2c, the SE (0.072) is lower than the RSW (0.226) and the significance value ($\beta =0.049$, p<0.05). Therefore, there is a positive and significant relationship between normative belief others behavior and purchase intention. Finally in H3, the SE (0.156) is smaller than SRW (0.906) and significance value also shows a positive relationship between purchase intention and purchase behavior. Thus, H2a, H2b, H2c and H3 are accepted. Whereas, H1 is rejected that was about the relationship between attitude and purchase intention.

Because, the study area was Bangladesh which is a collectivist cultural country that gives value to others opinion and thinking.

Table 6 : Summary and fitness of Structural Model

Hypothesis	Path Description	Standardized regression weight (SRW)	Scalar Estimates (SE)	CR (SRW)/(SE)	Significance Level	Result
H1	A→PI	.073	.094	.744	.457**	Rejected
H2a	MTC→PI	.280	.068	2.824	.005**	Accepted
H2b	NBOE→PI	.275	.063	2.196	.028*	Accepted
H2c	NBOB→PI	.226	.072	1.970	.049*	Accepted
H3	PI→PB	.906	.156	6.711	***	Accepted

($\chi^2(260)= 433.349$ ($p<0.001$); GFI=.886; IFI=.941; CFI=.909; TLI=.875; NFI=.868; RESEA=.059)

The collective self is founded on interpersonal relationships with others, which are formed through both common and symbolic identification with a group. Another reason is that the people of Bangladesh love to think about cultural welfare and development. In the context of pro-environmental behavior, persons displaying attachment to in-group membership such as pro-environmental groups may be more worried about environmental issues, and subjective norm may have a greater influence on purchase intention for ecologically sustainable items. In a collectivistic society like Bangladesh, subject norm would have a stronger influence on buying intention than attitude. Accordingly, the theory of reasoned action framework described buying intention and behavior for ecologically sustainable items in Bangladesh with good understanding in a concise and suitable method. Researchers such as Vermier and Verbeke (2008), Birgelen et al. (2009), and others have validated the TRA model's appropriateness.

Recommendations and Conclusion

Bangladesh is a country with a closely knitted population who are still in the pipeline of being educated and just being able to expose themselves to the availability of information. Purchasing or consuming green products is a relatively new concept for most people in the Bangladeshi market. From the study, we can conclude that Bangladesh has a collectivist culture, people here are very prone to affect and influenced by each other or their surroundings. So, the government and manufacturers with concerted effort can literate the population about perennial benefits of environmentalism, green knowledge, and green consumption. In the path of educating the population with green knowledge, concerned authorities can make the customers actively participate in their CSR activities related to saving the environment. It will eventually turn into a social norm and influence the people of Bangladesh to purchase more green products. Educating people about green knowledge is beneficiary for every stakeholder- the consumers will act consciously about any resource wastage, marketers can stress demand towards their products using eco-labeling, and ultimately the government will be able to ensure the maximum utilization of environmental resources. This study aims to identify the factors that influence Bangladeshi consumers to exert their green purchase behavior. The objective more precisely is to find out to what extent attitude, motivation to comply, normative belief others expectations, normative belief others behavior, purchase intention influence to exert green purchase behavior. The empirical data gathered during this study has been evaluated with the help of Ajzen's conceptual framework of TRA. According to Hofstede Insights Bangladesh has a culture of collectivism which means people here tend to give value to others' opinions and thinking. Studying the empirical data, it can be said that people of Bangladesh give value to the opinions of others like friends, family, colleagues, etc., so if their peer motivates them to buy green products, they will more likely be intended towards green consumption. In addition to that, it was also hypothesized that normative belief consisting of others' behavior and others' expectations will have a positive relationship with the purchase intention of green products. And this was accepted on the ground that people in Bangladesh tend to behave like what is expected from them in a group or how others are behaving in that

group. As a result, if there are increased numbers of groups of people advocating pro-environmental behavior the green purchase intention of the Bangladeshi market will be more prominent. Moreover, the empirical findings illustrate that those who have green knowledge tend to build a positive attitude toward green products. As a result, a strong intention to buy green products is eminent and this intention to buy green products turns into purchase. But the study also showed that in the Bangladeshi market people having a positive attitude only is not enough to exert into positive purchase intention of green products. Summarizing the discussion, we can come to the conclusion that the constructs subjective norm and purchase intention of the TRA model has more influence on the purchase behavior of green products than people's attitude toward green products from the perspective of the Bangladeshi market.

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